

The Impact of the Use of Smartphones and Social Networking Sites on Employees in the Private Sector

Author Details: Dr. Ahmed T Salman

Operation Manager/ Free Wireless LLC/ Cricket Wireless Authorized Dealer/USA

Master Project Manager.(MPM)

Certified International project manager.(CIPM)

Member at American Academy of Project management.(AAPM)

Abstract

The corporate sector is always driven by the need to increase productivity through the development and adoption of better policies, practices, and technologies. However, some of the changes in the socioeconomic environment threaten the capacity of a business in the corporate sector to achieve the required level of profitability. Smartphone technology is an aspect that defines modern-day society. The use of smartphone and social networking sites has increased immensely in the past decade. It can be attributed to the decreasing cost of the technology, increased research innovation in technology, and the contemporary culture that forces the approval of a smartphone. This research explores the impact of a smartphone and the use of social networking sites by employees in the private sectors with specific reference to the Cricket Wireless Company. A survey, a qualitative tool for data collection, is used to collect primary data through questionnaires. 100 employees at the Cricket Wireless Company respond to the inquiries. The data is coded and translated to a quantitative format to enable further statistical analysis. From data analysis, it is found that there exists a negative impact of smartphone and social networking sites where employees waste at least 24.74% of the time dedicated to work on such advances. The research calls for the implementation of external tools that can control the use of smartphone technology without distressing the productivity of employees

Keywords: *Social Networking, Smartphones, Private Sector, Time management, the productivity of employees.*

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

The objective of the Research

Technology has redefined the modern day human activities and tendencies with a significant shift from traditional methods to faster high-tech approaches. There is enough evidence to conclude that the adoption of technology has extended human abilities with a substantial positive impact (Nikoloski, 2014). However, as much technology is celebrated as one of the developments in human history that have empowered human beings, it is also labeled as a limiting factor by many. The corporate sector, both public and private, has been hit by technology. The cost-benefit analysis done by most economists shows that the positive and negative impacts of technology are substantial (Statista). It calls for the implementation of strict policies and ideas to help in the adoption of technology to limit its effects. Mobile technology has extended, and every single person in modern society understands the role it plays. According to Statista, there exist 2.32 billion smartphone users worldwide. The number of users is projected to reach 2.87 billion by 2020 (Statista). The trend has spread to other sectors, especially the commercial sector. Employees often use smartphones, and different employers have noted the course as a distraction that tends to affect the productivity of human resource. Some argue that it is instead productive and helps to quicken communication, allowing faster delivery of tasks.

Consequently, this research seeks to correctly assess the impact of using smartphones and social networking sites by the employees in the corporate sector. The company under consideration, Cricket Wireless Company, is a telecommunication firm located in the United States of America. As one of the best performing establishments in the market, it gives a reliable and extensive platform to assess the actual impact of the use of smartphones by human resources.

Background Study

The use of smartphones has stretched with an ever-changing technological environment. Inventors and mobile service providers are relentlessly funding research programs that only seek to make the smartphone more comprehensive (Farhadi & Ismail, 2012). In modern society, the smartphone has shifted focus on communication and has made mobile technology a vital tool capable of completing a lengthy listing of tasks. For instance, with a single click, a smartphone can perform complicated calculations or complete financial transactions that are comparatively costly in the traditional society. The benefits are worth appreciating. However, employees in the corporate sector when allowed the chance to access and use a smartphone at work freely, they tend to infringe on the over the productivity of the company. The hours dedicated to work and are often misquoted and misrepresented by the respective employee while using the smartphone. Research has also shown that smartphone technology with appealing apps can be addicted and therefore counterproductive. Social networking sites have extended in popularity with an ever-increasing number of users. In the corporate world, social networking sites have been identified as a leading platform for marketing and developing connections that extended the stretch of a business. Therefore, investors and managers have realized the sensitivity of the development and consequently proposed strategies and policies that promote the use of social networking sites for business. However, the results of allowing employees within the different department of a company have realized damaging effects. Productivity is often conflicting, and the adoption of the open use of smartphones has been labeled as a counterproductive strategy by managers in different companies. The case calls for an in-depth analysis to establish the benefits and challenges of using smartphones with intended to propose a lasting solution. Technology as a human creation cannot be constrained; the only solution focuses on the ability to develop strategies and tendencies that can help to cope up with the fast-growing world of technology.

Purpose of the Study

The primary goal of this research is to assess the impact of using a smartphone and social networking site by employees with specific consideration to Cricket Wireless Company. The assessment is an additional study to compliment and evaluate past research work that either categorized smartphone as productive or counterproductive.

Aims and Objectives

- i. To assess the impact of using smartphones in the corporate sector on employees.
- ii. To establish the effect of adopting policies and strategies that permit free using of smartphones at the workplace by employees.
- iii. To quantify the impact of overusing smartphones by the employee and how it reflects on the productivity of a business.

Research Questions

- i. What is the impact of using smartphones and social networking sites on employees in the private corporate sector?
- ii. Does the over-reliance on smartphones by the employees affect the financials of a company?
- iii. How can smartphones and social networking sites usage be adopted in the workplace without necessarily affecting the productivity of human resource and the overall financial rating of a company?

Proposed Research Methodology

In the study, a survey is used to collect primary data. It involves the distribution of questionnaires among a selected sample population of employees at Cricket Wireless Company. The sample population is arrived at based on a format that seeks to identify at least 10% of the employees cutting across all the departments in the company. Random sampling is used as per the pre-identified rules of sampling with regards to the objectives of the research. The rules cover the inclusion of all departments, age groups, and gender. The questionnaires are structured and presented to the sample population. The specific questions are simple and clear to inform better responses. The data collected is then coded and recorded in excel worksheet and later fed into the SPSS software for further statistical analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Since the study uses a survey as a method of data collection, there is the adoption of structures and policies to guard the social, economic, and political well-being of the respondents. Firstly, all the respondents are included in the study based on their signed consent. Any respondent that openly affirms a lack of permission is reserved and supplanted before the actual research. The respondents are also exposed to briefings to highlight on the key deliverable of the study and apprise them on their expectations. Additionally, credit is given to all the secondary material used to validate and discuss the topic of the research and the final results of the survey through correct referencing.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter examines sources related to the topic of study: the impact of smartphones and social networking sites on workers in the private sector. In reviewing this research, a case study of Cricket Wireless Company has been used to add emphasis to various aspects of the study. Advancement in smartphone technology has come with both positive and negative impacts. Additionally, social networking sites have become a growing phenomenon in the current world. Employees in both the private and public sectors have become "native speakers" of the digital language. Smartphones have made it more convenient for people to interact via networking sites. Private and public organizations have used these technologies to enhance their image and reputation. They post about their goals, mission, policies, duties, and other relevant information for the online users to see. On the other hand, the interaction has proved to be highly addictive and therefore distracting, especially to employees. Sources will be reviewed to show the impact of this phenomenon on both the public and private sectors. Then, the main ideas and a conclusion will be made at the end of the section.

2.2 Usage of Smartphones and Access to Social Media

Usage of smartphones and access to social media while at the workplace has become one of the most critical topics in the world. According to Proskauer (2014), the phenomenon has skyrocketed in popularity in recent times. Smartphones companies are always developing new, better and cheaper smartphones. Besides, social networking sites such as MySpace, Twitter, Linked-In, Facebook and Instagram have continued to grow stronger and influential in recent years. The rise of smartphones and social media usage has affected operation within organizations. Besides being a source of information and effective interaction, many employees have wasted much of their precious time using smartphones to access social media platforms at the expense of working. Mainly, this has hindered the achievement of organizational objectives and interest by distracting the focus of the employees. Organizations all over the world are all keen on curbing this negative impact and instead seize the advantage that comes with these technologies. Research carried out by Salary.com (2012), indicates that a whopping 64% of employees in both the public and private sector use to access sites not related to their work. Social media platforms such as Facebook is ranked high with 41% of the visits (Salary, 2012). It translates to wastage of time and resources.

2.3 Impacts on Employees in Public and Private Sector

The use of smartphones and networking sites sharpened employees' concentration span. According to Fahmy (2009), surfing the internet and interacting with others on social media use via smartphones enhanced concentration. The higher the frequency, the more efficient an employee becomes. The author backed up this claim with a research finding which stated that 65% percent of respondents in the research indicated that social media made them sharper and therefore more efficient workers (Fahmy, 2009). Sharpness and concentration span translate to higher productivity.

Employees in both the public and private sectors can acquire knowledge and insights through their smartphones when they access networking sites. The world consists of people with diverse ideas, and online interaction enhances the quality of these ideas. Through this interaction and communication, people within a network can exchange rich ideas and knowledge concerning their profession. They learn how to handle the issue and how to do their work innovatively. The social network, therefore, becomes a source of essential and relevant information. According to Gaal et al. (2015), knowledge is one of the critical factors that can enable organizations to compete favorably with others. The author adds that employees need to acquire vital

information and knowledge through interaction. The current dynamics in both the private and public sector call for informed employees to achieve their objectives promptly (Gaal et al., 2015).

The use of networking sites with smartphones also enhances secure communication, friendliness and therefore an openness among employees. In this case, it builds and strengthens personal relations between an employee and their mates. The networks do this by encouraging engagement while they are at work or even at home. They air out their views, listen to each other and form a cohesive team focused on common goals. Additionally, personal issues that may hinder effective working can be solved through this interaction.

Employees in public and private sector also use smartphones to access the social media which acts as a mental break. If used well, networking sites give employees a moment to relax their minds and reflect upon what they are doing. It breaks the monotony of working and ensures that they come back refreshed and more energized to work. According to Musso (2017), 34% of respondents in a study in the United States of America indicated that they access networking sites to take a mental break. The brake ensures that they are energized when they return to work, hence more productivity and performance.

Additionally, networking sites via smartphones enable employees to be innovative. According to Chu and Chan (2009), many constructive ideas that can be implemented at work are found on networking sites. Employees can, therefore, tap this idea to bring a change in society. Through these sites, an employee can learn how to solve primary life challenges in their day to day lives. For instance, an employee can access various blogs which can empower and give information on how to address multiple issues in their lives. In the long-run, this enhances their performance while at the workplace.

2.4 Employee Performance and Time Management

The use of smartphones and social networking sites at the workplace has an impact on productivity and hence employee performance. Employees in both the public and private sector have failed to produce good outcomes as stipulated by workplace policies. Munene and Nyaribo (2013) state that this habit leads to massive wastage of time, limiting productivity. The overall result, in this case, is a poor performance by employees. The authors emphasize the fact that employees are a vital asset to any organization. Organizations, in both the public and private sectors, largely depend on employees to gain a sharp competitive edge in an economic environment. How this employee reacts to technologies such as smartphones and networking sites directly affects the performance of the organizations (Munene & Nyaribo, 2013). Also, The University of Bergen (2014) states that four out of five employees use networking sites for their private reasons. The research further reveals that they usually do this while in the workplace. According to the author, using smartphones and other devices to access networking sites is a significant distraction to work while at the workplace (University of Bergen, 2014). Therefore, poor performance and wastage of time are evident.

According to Richard (2012), employees have adopted poor work practices and behavior while at the workplace via networking sites. Smartphones have facilitated this since they happen to be more convenient to use. Employers both in public and private sector have done their best to establish relevant technologies, but employees are misusing them. Following up insensible online discussions, chatting, and streaming irrelevant YouTube videos are some of the activities employees are engaged in while at the workplace. The author adds that these activities conflict with employee professional obligations which are the main reason why they are employed. Generally, this misbehavior leads to increased rebellion, blackmail and other negative traits that work against the goals and interests of the organization (Richard, 2012). Therefore, this leads to a situation whereby smartphones and networking sites are working against performance in an organization.

Smartphones and networking sites can negatively affect employee relations within an organization. The use of this technology has also changed the relationship between organizations and other vital players in an economic ecosystem. According to Ziger (n.d), malicious employees may use social media platforms with their smartphones to harass their mates and management. The behaviors negatively affect internal communication which is very paramount in both public and private organizations. In the long-run, it adversely affects the performance of the organization at large (Ziger, n.d). More is also wasted streamlining issues between employees in an organization.

On the contrary, some studies have stated that smartphones and social media platforms have a positive impact on performance. According to Fahmy (2009), employers who used networking sites were more productive than others. Those who are active on those platforms were perceived to be social and therefore good at solving problems. Those who did not use smartphones and other gadgets to access and interact via the media were said to be unproductive. According to the author, solutions are established through interactions (Fahmy, 2009). In this case, smartphones and networking sites can be used to enhance communication and boost productivity.

2.5 Overview

It is therefore evident that smartphones networking sites affects employees and respective organizations. Both the public and private sector are affected by these technologies. Mainly, it enhances interaction, knowledge sharing, problem-solving, and communication between employees and so on. On the other hand, networking sites and smartphones have led to wastage of time, adoption of unhealthy work practices, online harassment. All these affected the performance of an organization. If used well, these technologies can enhance organizational performance and success in both the private and public sector.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Overview

The research relies on primary qualitative data to collect information that helps define the set objectives. A survey is used where the selected population is allowed to give feedback on questionnaires from which the analysis is done. The data is then coded and translated to a quantitative format to allow further statistical analysis using the SPSS software. Research of this kind needs a hands-on perspective to evaluate and measure aspects that cannot be well-addressed through secondary research in including the use of systematic reviews or case studies. The Cricket Wireless Company is the basis of the study because it is one of the well-performing enterprises in the American economic society with a considerable number of employees that are recruitment about the laws. Equally, diversity as a concept of the modern-day society is well captured by the company. Therefore, it is logical to assume that the data collected through the survey has the required level of diversity, and it can be used to represent other enterprises in the American corporate market.

The data methodology is complete, and it is well-defined to be able to deliver the objectives of the research. There is focus on details and a general purpose of the data methodology to ensure the delivery of findings that would better define the association between the usage of smartphone technology and the productivity of employees in the work environment.

3.2 Survey

The survey represents a method of conducting research where the researcher prepares and administers questionnaires to the selected sample population. In this case, a standardized questionnaire is developed based on the goals of the study and the set of research questions. The latter is administered through a face-to-face interview where the respondents are allowed to interact with the researcher. As much as it is time-consuming, critical information that could otherwise be missed while using other methods of conducting the research is collected and adopted in the final results. Different reasons explain the choice of a survey as the basis for doing the research:

- i. It is effective and efficient
- ii. It offers more information through the unstructured face-to-face interaction.
- iii. The research also gets an opportunity to observe certain elements and aspects that help to define the findings of the investigation.
- iv. Limited ambiguity and vague information as the research can always seek clarification.
- v. It is more assured compared to other methods as the research can force the retrieval of specific information.

3.2.1. Inclusion Criteria:

- i. Must be an employee of the Cricket Wireless Company for at least one year.
- ii. Must be of sound mind and thought.
- iii. Must be working in a given department and have a list of duties and tasks to deliver on a daily basis.

3.2.2. Exclusion Criteria:

- i. Those that have only worked for the Cricket Wireless Company for less than one year.
- ii. Those on probation for violating specific rules and regulations of the company
- iii. Those that are only employed as consultants or experts and cannot claim a particular attachment to the company's primary structure.
- iv. Those that demonstrate a lack of opinion and thoughts, or have been diagnosed with certain brain dis-functionalities.

3.3 Questionnaire

A standard questionnaire was prepared and used in collecting data in the study. The choice of the survey as the best method is based on the assumption that most of the respondents will be willing to engage in an interview guided by a structured process. The questionnaire contains a list of six simple questions. Most of the issues only require a "Yes" or "NO" entry as the possible answer. The simplicity and brevity of the questionnaire are to help the respondents have an easy time sharing in the study and give the most basic response without too much thought. Being administered through a face-to-face interview, the researcher also helps define some of the vague ideas in the questionnaires, explain the questions, and seek further clarification, taking notes on the most critical aspects. The surveys were then analyzed and the data recorded in an excel worksheet. Given the nature of the data and the ability to code specific string variables into numerical variables, the data was converted into an SPSS file to permit further statistical analysis using the SPSS software. Some reasons informed the choice of the questionnaire as the primary tool in data collecting:

- i. Surveys are cheaper to prepare and administer compared to other methods of primary data collection, such as observation and one-on-one interviews.
- ii. The method also offers extensive coverage of data from the selected pool of respondents.
- iii. It is easy to administer as it requires minimal supervision.
- iv. When administered through a face-to-face setting, the researcher can seek clarification and make additional observations

3.4 Limitations of Survey

As much as the survey provides the best tool for collecting primary data, it has some drawbacks:

- i. The collection of information can be biased since it is based on the individual perspectives of the respondents.
- ii. It is time-consuming.
- iii. Critical structured elements are not identified in the data; it involves aspects that cannot easily be specific or essential ideas that are not captured through the structured questionnaires.
- iv. The scope of the research is limited to the questions outlined in the questionnaire
- v. The language barrier and risk of miscommunication when the respondent does not fully understand the problems or give inconsistent responses.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 Overview

The research is objective in the sense that it seeks to establish certain aspects of the collected data. The Cricket Wireless Company is utilized in the study as the basis of data the evaluation reflects the existing situation at the company. Given the nature of the research and the data collection tools used, it is critical to infer that the analysis of the data is extensive and objective. Descriptive statistics and other measures of association such as correlation analysis are used in the data analysis to make complete inferences that build on the world of research in the field of economics. In conducting the study and analysis of the collected data, there is a close reference to the existing pool of research material and a defined protocol that helps to guard the accuracy of the whole process. The analysis is set to achieve clear and precise results from the data collected and connect the statistical findings with the pre-established research questions. The essence of the process is to prove a bias that fully responds to the research questions and allows room for the development of scientific inferences.

4.2 Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics define the essential features of a data set in a study. It involves the definition of the characteristics of data that responds to simple questions on the topic under investigation. In this case, the problem is the assessment of the impact of the use of smartphones and social networking sites on the productivity employees of the Cricket Wireless Company. In retrospect, the analysis begins with the evaluation of the frequency of the usage of the smartphones and the social networking sites. Later on, the descriptive statistics seek to demonstrate the existing association between the set variables and measure the frequencies under each category as per the survey. The survey covers the main titles that are expressed through the questionnaire and coded to give numerical data that can permit easy statistical comparison and analysis.

From the data collected, there is a total of 100 participants. All of them take part in the survey and register their responses that are coded and translated to a data format that can allow further statistical analysis. From the study, the total frequency under each category of the variable is established at 100 (N=100). In accessing the percentage of the employees that own and use a smartphone, the analysis shows that 90% of the own employee smartphone and the 10% do not own smartphones. Being a tool that marks the modern day, the findings are consistent with other studies that also note the increasing popularity of smartphone technology. It can be attributed to the decreasing cost of such techniques given the increase in the number of companies offering the products in the market. Equally, a cultural change that has forced most of the people to adopt the smartphone technology to be connected to the world and relate to the modern society of telecommunication.

Possession of a smartphone

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
no	10	10.0	10.0	10.0
Valid yes	90	90.0	90.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.1: The percentage of employees at Cricket Wireless Company that own smartphones

With regards to the use of social networking sites, the analysis of the data indicates that over 50% of the employees are active users. The number of active social networking sites users also happen to be included in the name of employees that own a smartphone. From the interview responses, the use of social networking sites is considered a tool in the modern-day society that ensures global communication. Every employee that has social networking sites expresses confidence in the making the decision having realized the importance of such sites and how they provide connection to their entire world of information.

Social Networking Sites Users

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
no	44	44.0	44.0	44.0
Valid yes	56	56.0	56.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.2: The percentage of employees at Cricket Wireless Company that are active users of social networking sites

One important measure in the study is the addiction to smartphones. It directly reflects the productivity of the tool given the negative connotation of the term 'addiction.' Essentially, employees addicted to a smartphone cannot easily realize the set objectives at the workplace, hence a lasting adverse effect on the entire company in term of productivity and economic profitability. From data analysis, 64% of the respondents establish that the smartphone technology is, in fact, addictive, while 36% register a negative response to the question. The

disparity is high, hence a possible and informed conclusion that smartphone technology is addictive and therefore reflects negatively on the productivity of employees at Cricket Wireless Company.

Smartphone Technology Is Addictive

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	3	2.9	2.9	2.9
2	64	62.1	62.1	65.0
Total	36	35.0	35.0	100.0
	103	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.3: The percentage of employees at Cricket Wireless Company about the addictiveness of smartphone technology

The frequency of the usage of smartphone for social networking sites or any other reason is an indicator of the addition of the technology. From the collected data, 37% of the employees use their smartphones after every 10 minutes. With that high frequency, it shows that technology is of high distraction and affects the involvement of the employee in their work-related duties. From the analysis, only 10% of the employees rarely use smartphones. Assuming that every employee achieves the same results in unit time, only 2 out of 10 employees make the required level of efficiency in the workplace. The other eight are highly distracted and therefore their contribution the set organization goals restrained.

The Frequency of the Use of Smartphone and Social Networking Sites in Hours Per Day

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
After every 1 hour	12	12.0	12.0	12.0
After every 1-hour	8	8.0	8.0	20.0
After every ten mins	37	37.0	37.0	57.0
After every 2-4 hours	16	16.0	16.0	73.0
Valid After every 2-4hrs	6	6.0	6.0	79.0
Once per day	11	11.0	11.0	90.0
Rarely	8	8.0	8.0	98.0
Rarely	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.3: Frequency of the use of Smartphones and social networking sites in minutes per day

Employees demand a chance to measure and evaluate the impact of smartphone and social networking sites on their engagement and productivity at the workplace. From the data collected, 61% of the employees agree with the idea that smartphone technology and the use of social networking's sites affect the productivity of human resources at a workplace. 39% registers a contradicting opinion where the smartphone technology either does not change the productivity or increase the efficiency and hence better productivity for the company. All the responses are admissible since all the respondents in the research are well informed and offered their well-thought answers.

The Use of Smartphone and Social Networking Sites Reflects Negatively on Employees' Productivity

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid no	39	39.0	39.0	39.0
Valid yes	61	61.0	61.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.5: *The percentage of employees at Cricket Wireless Company about the effect of using smartphones and social networking sites on employee's productivity*

There is only one apparent fate of the research aimed at accessing the impact of a smartphone and the use of social networking sites on employees in the corporate world. It refers to the development and adoption of strategies to help discourage smartphone and shift the focus of employees away from social networking sites. From the data analysis, the results showing the percentage of employees that support the introduction of restrictions at workplace stands at 52% where the remaining 48% argue against the development or introduction of limiting protocols. The results define the effect of a smartphone as they tend to steal away hours of productive work from the employee. From a manager's perspective, employees are supposed to help achieve the set objectives of an enterprise, lest it makes losses in the economic market. Failure to adhere to the set protocols and complete the required level of productivity affects the entire establishment and risk its capacity to sustain itself in the long run.

The Adoption of Measures to Restrict the Use of Smartphones at the Workplace

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid no	48	48.0	48.0	48.0
Valid yes	52	52.0	52.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.6: *The adoption of measures to restrict the use of the smartphone at the workplace*

Analyzing the time an employee spends using the smartphone and social networking sites is a directly reflects the effect of the practice. From the data collected, the average time spent on smartphones and social networking sites by an employee at Cricket Wires Company is 111.8 minutes. The lowest score is 0 minutes, and the maximum score is 360 minutes, hence a range of 360 minutes. The minimum time spent on the smartphone can be explained in the case of employees that either does not own smartphones or are not registered on any social networking site. Therefore, they tend to focus their time on other activities. It is impractical to assume that such instances represent cases of employees that realize the higher productivity at the workplace. However, it makes logical sense to argue that those that spend most of their time using the smartphone and social networking sites sacrifice the time dedicated to other tasks and duties hence constraint productivity.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation	Variance
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Statistic
How much time do you spend on smartphone and social networking sites while at work in minutes	100	360	0	360	111.80	10.143	101.428	10287.636
Valid N (listwise)	100							

CHAPTER FIVE: DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS**5.1 Introduction**

Smartphones and social networking sites define the modern day social order. From the data collected, 90% of the employees at Cricket Wireless Company own smartphones and 56% of them are active users of the social networking sites available. The findings of the research collectively show the negative impact of the smartphone on productivity as most of the employees are forced to sacrifice time dedicated to work-related duties to using their smartphones or accessing social networking sites. As much as the research does not engage other financial information of the company in the effort to quantify the effects of smartphones on productivity, it is evident that there exists a considerable; the degree of impact that needs to be covered through well established policies and practices. In this section, the research question weighted against the findings from data analysis. The results are also extracted and critically evaluated in the face of the existing research conducted in the past. The aim is to offer critical and more informed inferences that seek to provide an enduring response to the course. The section also highlights the limitations of the study and provide recommendations for future research.

5.2 Research Questions

What is the impact of using smartphones and social networking sites on employees in the private corporate sector?

About this research question, the basis of the study is to establish the effect of smartphone technology and social networking sites on employees. Employees are given tasks and responsiveness and working in a different department active the collective goals of the company. The effectiveness of an employee is measured by the unit output concerning the time where the more one achieves in less time, the more productive they are. From the analyzed data, 61% of the employees argue that smartphone and social networking sites reflect negatively on the productivity of the employee. On the hand, 39% of the respondents say against the idea that smartphones affect the capacity of the employee to deliver their tasks. Therefore, the research establishes that there exists an adverse effect of the smartphone on human resources that by extension limits the scope of human resources to match the set goals and objectives in any given establishment.

Does the over reliance on smartphones by the employees affect the finances of a company?

Given the nature of the research, it is hard to quantify the association between the usage of smartphones and the finances of a company. However, when the productivity of the employees is assumed to in a direct relationship with the company's financial status, it is possible to infer, from the data collected, that extensive use of smartphone negatively affects the productivity of a company. In estimating the amount of time and the frequency of using the smartphone by the employees, the research shows that an average of 118.80 minutes is

spent on a smartphone by employees while at the workplace. Given that each worker is expected to work for 8 hours a day, the research shows that the time spent on smartphone represents 24.74% of the total amount of time dedicated to work-related responsibilities. Therefore, the productivity of every employee is negatively affected by the same percentage (24.74%) assuming that the same effort is spared across all the hours dedicated to work and every unit of work achieved a given level of productivity and profitability. Basing on the results, a company can be able to extend its productivity by merely developing and adopting policies that limit and restrict the use of smartphones at work. However, the approach presents a case where the employees are denied the chance to get connected to the world or communicate with friends and families. It is a tough and a twisted decision to make given the general acceptance of technology by different consumers in the market. Instead, companies tend to encourage the adoption of new technologies to extend productivity and cultivate a human resource that is more informed on technology, and that can champion sustainability.

From the data analysis, 52% of the employees support the adoption of policies to restrict the use of the smartphone while 48% discourage such measures. The world is shifting, and companies that are more drawn to technologies tend to gain more presence in the market. According to Ratchford (2001), customer preferences are not only defined by prices but the wholeness of a product and the company in question. Some customers only seek products that match specific qualities. For instance, a considerable number of customers when selecting which network provider company to engage, consider their efficiency of customer services and the general technology used. Therefore, imposing limitation only defies the objective of championing innovation and technology in the face of the new world.

How can smartphone and social networking sites usage be adopted in the workplace without necessarily affecting the productivity of human resource and the overall financial rating of a company?

It is essential to address the most crucial aspects of the study; the best approaches to tackling the situation without affecting the employees or the company. In accessing the topic, there are two groups with different preferences that tend to contradict. The company wants to make more profits by subjecting the employee to specific roles and duties and making sure that they devote all their attention to their positions. The employees apart from responding to their responsibilities are human beings often feel the urge of communicating and using social networking sites while at work. There must be an existing balance or a way to propose and impose a policy where all the parties get covered. It calls for more research on the possible intervention that companies can use to control, the use of smartphones. Authoritative approaches and restriction only reflect poorly on the welfare of the employees as there is always the need to promote expressionism and allow employees to connect with their families while at work. Some companies have devoted resources to creating centers and individual rooms where employee during a specific period get the chance to use smartphones and access social networking sites. For such companies, the policy has ensured good relations and has promoted a culture characterized by commitment and shared dedication to realizing the set organizational goals.

5.2 Limitations of the Study

The study accesses the impact of the smartphone on the employees in the chosen company, Cricket Wireless Company. As much as the investigation is objective, the population used is limited compared to the tremendous corporate world with a multitude of the protocol employed by different companies to oversee the adoption of technologies by the employees. Human Resource Management is an independent field that has since defined practices and ideas that are mostly employed by managers to help restrict employees and manage their advances. Therefore, it is impractical to infer the results of the study of the large population due to the existing gaps. The population size is limited and cannot be efficient to present the current condition for all the employees in the corporate sector. Therefore, there is a need to restructure, and direct research in the same is to cover an extensive sample population and various more effective tools to analyze and present the comprehensive data. It will offer better-placed inference that reflects the position of employees when subjected to the use concept of smartphone technology and the spread of social networking sites.

Survey as the primary tool in the research for data collection does not offer extensive coverage of the aspects that can be of critical importance to the study. The respondents are only limited to the developed questions in the questionnaire hence limited room to include information that could help change the course of research. However, the choice of the survey was to help break down the extended scope of the topic into manageable parts. It helps to achieve the specificity required and allows the results and data analysis to respond to the set research questions. Nevertheless, the limitation imposes a challenge that limits the research ability to define ideas that are yet to be exposed in past research work. The limited focus as much as it achieves specificity limits the scope of the study and denies the exploration of concepts that could reestablish new ideas and challenge the existing knowledge on the topic.

5.3 Recommendations

Smartphone technology is an innovation that has realized tremendous positive impacts on the sociology-economic environment. Therefore, there exists the possibility of the technology to be assimilated in the corporate sector and still perform efficiently. To achieve this, there need for more research in defining practices and other related innovations that can make the smartphone technology work better for the corporate sector. One possible option is the investment in applications that can link employees with some of their tasks. Employees can use smartphones not only to access the social networking sites but also lengthen their contribution to the overall organizational goals at the workplace.

5.4 Conclusion

Smartphone technology has spread with increasing number of users. The case can be attributed to the ever-decreasing price of smartphones and other related technologies. In the research, the impact of smartphones and the use of social networking sites on employees is estimated about the Cricket Wireless Company. From that data collected, it is evident that at least 90% of employees on smartphones and over 50% are active users of different social networking sites. The research further explores the impact of smartphones on the employee where 24.74% of the time dedicated to work is instead spent on smartphone and social networking sites by an employee. The results show that productivity is affected by 24.74%, assuming that with the elimination of smartphones the employees would spend all their time on work-related duties.

Statically, there is a reason to ensure the adoption of policies and measures that can restrict the use of smartphones and social networking sites at the workplace. However, the world is shifting to a more diverse perspective that promotes the expressionism and appreciates the role of technology. Therefore, finding a way to deal with the smartphone at the workplace and allow employees to have the freedom of accessing and using social networking sites is essential. Employers apart from subjecting employees to use authoritative rule can use more democratic interventions ways of solving conflicts and establishing good relations. Nevertheless, there is a need to conduct more research in the same are to find more assuring solution to the problem that would serve the shared organizational objectives.

References

- i. Chu, K.-M., & Chan, H.-C. (2009). *Community-based innovation: Its antecedents and its impact on innovation success*. *Internet Research*, 19(5), 496-516.
- ii. Fahmy, M. (2009). *Facebook, YouTube at work make better employees*. Retrieved from http://tech.yahoo.com/news/nm/20090402/wr_nm/us_work_internet_tech_life
- iii. Farhadi, M. & Ismail, R. (2012). *Information and Communication Technology Use and Economic Growth*. *PLoS ONE* 7(11). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0048903>
- iv. Gaál, Z, Szabó, L, Obermayer-Kovács, N., & Csepregi, A. (2015). *Exploring the role of social media in knowledge sharing*. *The Electronic Journal of Knowledge Management*, 13(3), 185-197) available online at www.ejkm.com
- v. Munene, A. G., & Nyaribo, Y. M. (2013). *Effect of social media participation in the workplace on employee productivity*. *International Journal of Advances in Management and Economics*, 2(2), 141-150.

vi. Nikoloski, K. (2014). *The role of information technology in the business sector*. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 3(12), 303- 309.

vii. Proskauer. (2014). *Social media in the workplace around the world 3.0*. Retrieved from <http://www.proskauer.com>: <http://www.proskauer.com/files/uploads/social-media-in-the-workplace-2014.pdf>

viii. Ratchford, B. (2001). *The economics of consumer knowledge*. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 27(4), 397-411. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1086/319617>

ix. Richards, J. (2012). *What has the internet ever done for employees? A review, map and research agenda*. *Emerald*, 34(1), 22-43.

x. Salary.com. (2012). *Wasting time at work 2012*. Retrieved from <http://www.salary.com>: <http://www.salary.com/wasting-time-at-work-2012/>

xi. Statista. 'Number of smartphone users worldwide from 2014 to 2020 (in billions)'. Retrieved from: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/330695/number-of-smartphone-users-worldwide/> Accessed 29th August 2018.

xii. The University of Bergen. (2014, November 13). *Use of private social media affects work performance*. *Science Daily*. Retrieved August 28, 2018, from www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2014/11/141113085146.htm

xiii. Zeiger, Stacy. (n.d.). *The Disadvantages of Social Networking in the Workplace*. *Small Business - Chron.com*. Retrieved from <http://smallbusiness.chron.com/disadvantages-social-networking-workplace-21064.html>

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Questionnaire

1. *Tick on the correct response! Gender: Male Female
2. Do you own a smartphone? Yes, No
3. a). Do you happen to use social networking sites? Yes No
b). How often do you use social networking sites for hours while at work?
4. How often do you use a smartphone for any other reasons?
After every 10 minutes
After every one hour
After every 2-4 hours
Everyday
Rarely
5. Are smartphone and the use of social networking sites addictive? Yes No
6. Do you support the adoption of restrictions to correct the excessive use of smartphones by the Cricket Wireless Company management? Yes No
Why?.....
.....
.....